

MEASURING TRADE UNION EFFECTIVENESS IN THE RMG INDUSTRY IN BANGLADESH: THE MEDIATING EFFECTS OF BUYERS' CODES OF CONDUCT

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Received on 17 October 2021, Accepted on 20 June 2022, Published on 31 July 2022
Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6699713

Abstract

The purposes of this study are to measure the relative importance of organizational effectiveness (OE), collective bargaining effectiveness (CBE), industrial relations climate effectiveness (IRCE) with the effectiveness of trade unions (TUs) and to examine the mediating effects of buyers' codes of conduct (BCoC) on TUs. This study has been conducted using a positivism paradigm and cross-sectional survey design. Based on the literature and conceptual model, ten hypotheses were drawn. A structured questionnaire with closed-ended questions was developed, designed, and surveyed and had 276 responses with an answer rate of 62.73% using the convenience sampling technique. A partial least square (PLS) based structural equation modeling (SEM) approach is used to analyze the data. The study finds a significant positive relationship between the OE, CBE, IRCE, BCoC, and TUs effectiveness where BCoC results mediation relationships of OE, CBE, IRCE, and TUs effectiveness, and such mediation increase the effectiveness of TUs in protecting the rights of the workers in the RMG industry in Bangladesh. The findings of this study have significant policy implications in the Bangladeshi context.

Keywords : *Collective Bargaining Effectiveness, Industrial Relations Climate Effectiveness, International Buyers, Organizational Effectiveness, Trade Unions Effectiveness.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The growth of the Ready-Made Garment (RMG) industry is creating, now, a huge employment opportunity for semi-skilled and unskilled rural people (Akter & Banik, 2018; Meyer et al., 2021). RMG exports from Bangladesh increased by 28.02 percent to United States Dollar (USD) 19.900 billion in the first six months of fiscal 2021-22 compared to exports of \$15.545 billion in the same period of the previous fiscal 2020-2021 (EPB, 2021). Therefore, Bangladesh has already occupied the position of second-largest apparel exporting country in the world (Islam, 2021). Many studies show that most garments factories fail to gain success because of their unwillingness to improve the working conditions of the workers (Ahad et al., 2021).

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Poor working environment, unskilled workforce, political instability, low wages, inadequate infrastructure are responsible for creating instability in the RMG making huge losses to owners as well as to the government exchequer (Islam et al., 2020). The necessities of industrial workers are freedom from fear, security of work, and freedom from needs (Swazan & Das, 2021). An environment, where they are placated with their works, guaranteed a secured future, and gave their essential requirements in life implies an environment of good industrial relations (IRs) (Van Buren et al., 2021). A conceptual aspect of industrial relations (IRs) includes the organizational interactions and relationships among its actors i.e. employers, employees and their association (trade union), buyers, and the government (Tapia et al., 2015).

The trade union (TU) is a voluntary employee association to defend and upholds members' mutual interests through collective bargaining to ensure fair wages, security of a job, and better working conditions (Baral, 2018). They also protect their members from any injustice and exploitation, and against any violation by their employers (Trebilcock, 2020). The collective platform of the workers' TUs plays a significant role in protecting workers' rights and interests such as improving working conditions, ensuring safety and wages (Risak, 2017). The established TUs assist their members by sharing their knowledge and experience. This assistance develops the tools to serve the members by upholding members' rights and interests. Moreover, such type of assistance generates power to the mind of the workers' help in getting together in the workplace to talk about common problems. Therefore, collective decisions regarding the solutions of the problems of workplace issues can be democratically taken and put these views to the employer (Trebilcock, 2020).

Trade unions also find solutions that meet the business needs of the employers while the employers treat workers' rights fairly. When the workers become unhappy at work then TUs give employees a voice of supporting and improving their retention and reducing absenteeism (Ford, 2019). Unionized workplaces provide workers a satisfied mindset to work in their jobs for a longer time and such satisfaction helps to use their time at work more productively. Moreover, unions not only present themselves for keeping the interests of the workers but also for the organizations (Anner, 2020). TUs assist with the many workplace issues that can be very useful to organizations. The experienced union representatives can provide consultation services gathered from the perceptions of the workers to the organization to make better-informed business decisions (Alam et al., 2018).

The roles, powers, and efficiencies of TUs in protecting and promoting workers' rights and interests were very frustrating particularly in RMG industry in Bangladesh before the collapse of the Rana Plaza building in Dhaka on 24th April 2013 (Kabir et al., 2019). Currently, the scenario has been changed particularly after the Rana Plaza tragedy. Now TUs play a valuable role in establishing jovial relationships between owners and employees in the Bangladesh RMG sector (Barua et al., 2021). Although there is a general perception that TUs in RMG industry in Bangladesh do not play their proper roles in keeping the rights of their members or workers (Barua & Ansary,

2017). Therefore, TUs experienced various difficulties radiating from declining power membership (Alam et al., 2020). For this, TUs in RMG industry in Bangladesh need to be concerned to find out the ways of effectiveness and enhancement of their positions. Therefore, the matter of union effectiveness has become a more focused issue in the working environment.

Trade unions help workers to address members' problems; make them aware of their responsibilities and rights to create a sound workplace environment (Rahim, 2017). It bargains with management over the privileges and rewards of the workers (Ullah, 2015). The TUs draw awareness from the community, government agents (GAs), and others concerning if the employers do not value their claim (Klasen, 2019). Therefore, TUs are an effective medium for employees to raise their voices and protection of the rights of workers in Bangladesh's RMG sector (Sultan et al., 2020). It is equally crucial that workers continue to recognize TUs as an opportunity and collaborate with them to build a workplace unity that benefits both employees and businesses (Alam et al., 2004).

The Rana Plaza factory building collapsed killing 1,133 people and critically injuring thousands more; in the years before the Rana Plaza building collapse, numerous fatal factory fires occurred in Bangladesh (Uddin, 2020). In response to this and other disasters within the Bangladesh RMG industry, international retailers joined with TUs and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to create the Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh (the "Accord") (Beierlein, 2020). The Accord is a legally binding agreement among the retailers supplied by Bangladesh RMG factories to create and fund a system for factory inspection and repair.

The Accord is overseen by a steering committee made up of equal members representing the signing retailers' TUs, chaired by a neutral representative chosen by the International Labor Organization (ILO) (Cook et al., 2019). In order to export RMG, it is not only the quality parameters that are important towards acceptance of the product as per the intended end use, but also the working environment in which the garments are to be produced is equally important so that the sweatshop concept is taken care of and the code of conduct must be stretched towards achieving the objectives of social compliance issues. Currently, many international buyers are demanding compliance with their "code of conduct" before placing any garment import order. In light of growing competition among RMG exporting countries and consumer preference for products that meet internationally recognized social standards, Bangladesh's RMG suppliers need to comply with the codes of conduct of the buyers (Baral, 2010). Therefore, the pressure from the international buyers regarding the compliance of their codes of conduct relating to the workers' safety and rights is one of the major issues and helps to boost the TUs of the sector under study.

Many studies have been conducted on TUs in RMG industry in Bangladesh. The studies paid attention to the roles of TUs towards the employees' living standards and fair labor practices along with their importance (Nayak et al., 2019). Other scholars paid attention to the effect of TUs on the socio-economic condition of

Bangladesh, the relationship between the workers and owners, and the violations of TUs' rights (Anner, 2020). However, there is a lack in the literature in proving the effectiveness of the TUs in the workplaces of the workers. Moreover, to the best of the knowledge of the researchers, there is no well documentation regarding the effectiveness of TUs in protecting workers' rights in the field of RMG industry in Bangladesh. Therefore, there is the need to increase understanding of the perceptions of the workers regarding the effectiveness of TUs in their rights keeping. Moreover, there is a gap in previous literature on the mediating effects of BCoC through the OE, CBE, and IRCE on TUs effectiveness in the RMG industry in Bangladesh. In view of the above problems, the main question of this study is: what are the perceptions of workers on the effectiveness of TUs in protecting their rights in the RMG industry in Bangladesh? In addition, what are the mediating effects of BCoC on the Trade Union Effectiveness (TUE)?

Hence, this study measures the relative importance of the effectiveness of TUs in protecting and promoting workers' rights in the RMG industry in Bangladesh from the perception of workers. Moreover, this study intends to examine the mediating effects of BCoC on the effectiveness of TUs in protecting workers' rights in the sector under study. This study will add more information to the literature of TUs and improve the understanding of the knowledge of TUs effectiveness. This study will also provide the result regarding the workers' perceptions towards the effectiveness of TUs in addressing and protecting the workers' rights in the RMG industry of Bangladesh and assist this collective platform of workers to advance their strategies. This research work will be helpful to the policy-makers and academics as a reference point. This study also will provide guidelines regarding future research in this field.

2. CONCEPTUAL MODEL AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

The union's effectiveness indicates a TU that is flourishing and competent in the representation of employees at the time of addressing and safeguarding workers' rights (Bednarowicz, 2019; Mzangwa, 2013). Jha and Kumar (2020) and Sinha (2017) mentioned that there must have a good industrial relations climate, internal union democracy, and internal functional efficiency statutory recognition, goals, and practical implications to obtain those goals to make the TUs be effective. Durazzi (2018) and Pyman et al. (2010) showed their works that enriched working terms and conditions, union density, union leadership style, union voice, and industrial democracy bring the effectiveness of TUs. The literature gets the view that TUs effectiveness can be measured using different types of constructs. Kgaphola (2017) defines TUs effectiveness as 'members' perceptions of a union's performance in negotiation for extrinsic benefits (economic), intrinsic benefit (non-economic), and being responsive to its members. According to Van Roozendaal (2020) most preceding studies find out TUs effectiveness in stipulations of functional activities maintained by the TUs such as addressing employees' grievances, decision-making authority, providing proper employment, providing a favorable work environment, and protecting members from unfair dismissals from the organization.

Bryson (2003) cited in Chidzambwa (2015) mentioned that organizational and collective bargaining effectiveness can bring TUs effectiveness. In this study organizational effectiveness is termed as the capacity of the unions as the collective organization to capture those factors which represent its members under its healthy condition as an organization. This study also defined the term collective bargaining effectiveness as the capability to bring or organize better working terms and conditions of the workers. Tarumaraja et al., (2015) found that union effectiveness is significantly affected by effective union organization. Pyman et al., (2010) and Shamir et al. (2018) emphasized that organizational effectiveness brings by the influence of environmental effectiveness. Environmental influences incorporated with the level of hidden requirements for union services, the degree of employer opposition to unions, and employment growth. It also includes democratic structures, bureaucracy, innovation, and representational specialization (Pyman et al., 2010). Bryson (2003) and Hvidman (2019) postulated that organizational effectiveness can negatively or positively affect the service delivered by a TU. The study conducted by Bryson and Forth (2017) found that there is a significant correlation between organizational and TUs effectiveness from the viewpoint of employee perceptions in safeguarding or protecting their rights such as fair pay, promoting equal opportunities, protecting workers, making work interesting, and enjoyable, and working with management to increase quality and productivity.

Effective collective bargaining among the TUs, workers, and employers or management over the terms and conditions of the employment can provide sound industrial relations among the parties (Atzeni, 2021; Traxler, 1994). The effective function of collective bargaining among the actors of IRs brings an impact on wage dispersion and income inequalities (Johnston & Land-Kazlauskas, 2018). Moreover, collective bargaining can get better the standard of the employment relationship between the workers, management, employers, and the firms as well (Kuruvilla & Li, 2021). This function of the TUs can be a constructive instrument for bringing more stable working relations to ensure industrial peace which leads to a more efficient allocation of resources greater motivation and ultimately productivity in the respective industry or organization (Cazes et al., 2019). While preparing the questionnaire questions have been set to know the perceptions of the respondents about the effectiveness of TUs from the aspect of collective bargaining in the RMG industry of Bangladesh.

Bryson (2003) cited in Chidzambwa (2015) mentioned that collective bargaining effectiveness can bring TUs effectiveness. Collective bargaining helps to enter a mutual agreement that might change pay rates, working hours, working standards, workplace protection, health and social security, the share of productivity (Johnston & Land-Kazlauskas, 2018). The right to collective bargaining with an employer strengthens the individual rights, equality, and sovereignty of employees by providing them the ability to affect the setting of laws on the job and thereby obtain power over a significant element of their lives, namely their jobs (Jackson et al. 2016). The effectiveness of TUs of the RMG industry can be ensured and enhanced by the

inclusiveness of collective bargaining by reducing inequality and making sure proper practices of labor regulations in order to have labor protection (Ahlquist & Mosley, 2021; Chan & Hui, 2014).

It's a common understanding that a harmonious working atmosphere of an organization leads to industrial peace ensures efficient allocation of resources, satisfaction, motivation, and behavior patterns of individuals in the workplace (Aloisi & De Stefano, 2020). Such a harmonious working atmosphere is termed as the industrial relations climate which is affected by a set of causal variables. From an assessment of the literature on TUs-employers-management relations, some potential climate extent that affects the effectiveness of TUs in protecting the rights and interests of their members (Doucouliagos, 2017; Dastmalchian et al., 1989). A handful of studies by De Prins et al. (2020) Dastmalchian et al. (1982); Gandz and Whitehead (1981); Kelly and Nicholson (1980); Nicholson (1979); Warr et al. (1978) utilized the concept of industrial relations climate as one portion of organizational climate connected with the norms and attitudes reflecting management-union relationships. Industrial relations climate can bridge the theoretical gap between employee relations outcomes and organizational characteristics such as disputes and occurrence of strikes (Addison & Teixeira, 2017).

Parties who are purchasing products and services are buyers (Ali et al. 2021). Foreign buyers are importers of final goods according to their requirements (Sarkar, et al. 2020). In the RMG industry, foreign buyers enforce not only order-based requirements but also overall operational climate specific to manufacturers such as working hours, protection of workers, occupational atmosphere, contamination of the climate, manufacturing cycle, procurement of raw materials, quality management and regulation, social responsibility, etc (Islam et al., 2014; Rahim, 2017). Buyers' code of conduct (BCoC) are the principles that can be the effective measures across the industry for ensuring the health, safety, and welfare, the right to collectively assemble and negotiate, letter of employment, and the minimum wage for the RMG employees (Ansary & Barua, 2015). Compliance with foreign buyers is an important requirement for the success of the RMG manufacturers (Tarannum & Ansary, 2018; Alamgir & Banerjee, 2019) for bringing peaceful IRs. For effective trade unions, the organization needs to disclose to the concerned parties regarding its compliance decisions (Alam et al., 2018). Finally, compliance guarantees all human rights and services according to the international buyers' CoC (Ahamed, 2013). Accord on Fire and Building Safety and Alliances for Bangladesh Workers Safety-these two alliances of international buyers and their CoC have also significant effect on the RMG sector of Bangladesh which creates sound IRs, thereby growing the green RMG industry for the betterment and interests of the effective TUs (Hasan, 2018).

Based on the literature the following framework has been developed to measure the effectiveness of TUs in maintaining workers' rights in the RMG industry in Bangladesh. Based on the literature, the conceptual research framework mentioned in figure 1 is to be used to develop the hypotheses and survey questionnaire for the quantitative part of this study.

Source : Bryson (2003:6); Gall and Fiorito (2016:202) and Dlamini (2018:11)

Figure 1 : Conceptual Framework of the Study

From figure 1, a number of possible relations among OE, CGE, IRCE, and BCoC and TUs effectiveness in the RMG industry of Bangladesh are drawn. Ten hypotheses are then generated accordingly.

H1a: OE has a positive relationship with the Effectiveness of TUs.

H1b: OE has a positive relationship with BCoC.

H2a: CBE has a positive relationship with the Effectiveness of TUs.

H2b: CBE has a positive relationship with BCoC.

H3a: IRCE has a positive relationship with the Effectiveness of TUs.

H3b: IRCE has a positive relationship with BCoC.

H4: BCoC has a positive relationship with the Effectiveness of TUs.

H5: BCoC will mediate the relationship between OE and the Effectiveness of TUs.

H6: BCoC will mediate the relationship between CBE and the Effectiveness of TUs.

H7: BCoC will mediate the relationship between IRCE and the Effectiveness of TUs.

3. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

3.1 Design and Sampling Technique

This is a cross-sectional study in which data were gathered at a single point in time (Uma Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Data were collected from the workers of RMG industry of Bangladesh to understand their perceptions concerning the effectiveness of TUs in protecting the rights of workers in the sector. Moreover, this study is correlational, which is designed to explore a relationship, association, or interdependence among the independent and dependent variables (Kothari, 2004; Uma Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The collected data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares (PLS) based structural equation model (SEM). Convenience sampling, which is also known as the judgmental sampling technique, has been used to select the sample of this study. According to Ali et al. (2016) and Sekaran and Bougie (2016), convenience sampling is effective in exploratory research and is considered the best way of getting basic information efficiently and quickly.

3.2 Sample Design

This study has been conducted using 276 questionnaires with an answer rate of 54.50%. Advocates of PLS claim that it has the ability to estimate research models using small samples with no strict distribution assumptions and can model both reflective and formative constructs within the same research model. According to Fornell and Bookstein (1982) and Willaby et al. (2015) PLS-SEM works efficiently with small sample sizes when models are complex. Moreover, Sarstedt and Cheah (2019) state that PLS-SEM can be applied with smaller samples in many instances when other methods fail. Such justification motivates us to conduct our work using 276 respondents. This sample size fulfills the necessary condition of the required sample size i.e., 205 respondents by taking into account 99% confidence level, standard deviation of 0.5, and $\pm 1\%$ margin of error. According to Westland's (2010) software the minimum sample size for our SEM model is 150 cases at 0.3 predicted effect sizes, 0.80 desired statistical power level, 5 constructs, 34 observed variables, and 0.05 likelihood level (Soper,2020). Moreover, according to Hill (1998), a sample size above 200 is enough for sufficient data analysis at 5% level of significance. Accordingly, 276 respondents were considered satisfactory. Table 1 provides the demographic profile of respondents.

Table 1 : Respondents' Profile

Demographic characteristic		% (N=276)	Demographic Characteristic		% (N=276)
Gender	Male	41.30%	Years for worked in RMG Industry	Less than 2 Years	13.80%
	Female	58.70%		+2 to 5 Years	9.40%
Age	18-25 Years old	44.60%		+5 to 10 Years	42.00%
	26-33 Years old	43.10%		+10 and Above	34.80%
	34-41 Years old	10.50%	Monthly Salary	BDT 8000-13000	8.70%
	>41 Years old	1.80%		BDT 14000-19000	10.50%
Marital Status	Unmarried	22.80%		BDT 20000-25000	34.10%
	Married	77.20%		BDT 26000-31000	28.60%
Education	Below SSC	44.60%		BDT 32000-37000	11.60%
	Below HSC	40.60%	BDT 43,000 and Above	6.50%	
	Below Bachelor	10.10%			
	Below Maters	2.90%			
	Masters	1.80%			

3.3 Questionnaire Development

To investigate the significant factors and to test the hypothesized relations among the constructs, a questionnaire was developed and designed. For conducting, the survey this study used a structured questionnaire with closed-ended questions. A 6-point Likert scale questionnaire was intended to measure the factors and variables of the effectiveness of TUs. A 6-point scale has been chosen because they allow for improved measuring precision (Li, 2013; Nemoto & Beglar, 2014). Moreover, middle categories cause statistical issues in that rating scale analyses sometimes indicate that neutral categories interrupt calculation in a way that they do not match statistical models well or are disordered. In addition, a neutral category is needless because studies should include only things on a questionnaire that respondents should answer, and this should be verified by piloting (Wolfe & Smith, 2007). A 6-point Likert scale ranging from 6=strongly agree to 1=strongly disagree was used on the 34 observed items adapted from Cazes et al. (2019); Dastmalchian et al. (1989); Dlamini (2018) and Mohamed et al. (2010) in their researches.

3.4 Data Collection Procedure

The researchers collected the data physically and using an online-based google form for almost three months. The respondents are selected purposively from the 80 TUs of Dhaka and Gazipur industrial areas, which are registered in the Department of Labor out of 909 registered TUs for this survey. In this study, total 440 questionnaires were distributed to the members of the 80 TUs. The questionnaire was distributed personally through the researcher directly to the potential respondents. Out of 440 questionnaires 70 were distributed electronically using google form link to respondents' email, WhatsApp, and Facebook Messenger. In the case of the face-to-face data collection procedure, total 370 questionnaires were distributed. From the 290 collected questionnaires, 276 were used of which 30 were responded by the google form and the rest 246 are collected from face-to-face surveys. In the face-to-face data collection procedure, the response rate is 66.49% and the rate of online is 42.86%. The average response rate of the questionnaires is 62.73%. According to Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004), there is no standard definition for a minimum acceptable response rate. Therefore, the response rate of 62.73%.for this study has been considered satisfactory. Moreover, of the 440 distributed questionnaires, 164 remained unresponsive due to the pandemic COVID 19 crisis.

3.5 Data Analysis Tools

Cross-sectional studies of relationships between attitudes and behaviors are vulnerable to common method variance (CMV) inflation of correlations. Method biases can have a major effect on their reliability, validity of products, and covariation between latent constructs (Podsakoff et al., 2012). This study used Harman's Single Factor test based on the social research method conducted by Becker et al., (2012). If the common latent factor explains more than 50% of the variance, then common method bias may be present (Eichhorn, 2014). This study accounted for only 34.047% of

the variance; thus, here common method was not a persistent dilemma. Next, the inter-correlations presented no value of 0.9 or more with the highest inter-correlation at only 0.871. Thus, both tests address that method bias is not a major issue in the study. Researchers used SPSS version 23.0 to process the descriptive statistics and reliability analysis of the collected data and to assess the demographic profile of the sample and the internal consistency of the constructs. Further, for analyzing the research model, researchers used PLS analysis with Smart PLS 3.0 software. Approaching the suggested two-stage analytical procedures for SEM, researchers tested the measurement model (validity and reliability of the measures) and then examined the SEM (Hair et al., 2017a). The significance of the path coefficients and the loadings are tested using a bootstrapping method (5000 resample) (Hair et al., 2017a).

4. DATA SURVEY AND ANALYSIS

The surveyed data were analyzed from the perspective of two dimensions such as i) assessment of measurement model and ii) assessment of structural model by using SEM technique (Chin, 1998). Figure-1 illustrates the model. During the survey on the union members of RMG industry 276 respondents' questionnaires were finalized with data collected for 34 items using this questionnaire. The indicators of this study are reflective of why PLS technique is designed to accommodate reflective constructs (Fornell & Bookstein 1982).

4.1 Assessment of Measurement Model

As a systematic methodological process, canonical correlations analysis (CCA) is used in confirming measurement models in PLS-SEM. To assess the measurement model convergent and discriminant validity was used. In this study, such validity measurement techniques were used.

4.1.1 Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is the technique of measuring the correlations of the constructs, which indicates the reliability of the observed items. The higher values of the convergent validity ensure the strong correlation of the items in each construct. There are three steps to determine the reliability of the items in each construct. From them, first is to assess the indicator loadings and their significance where the threshold of 0.60 in the association of t-statistic above ± 1.96 for a two-tailed test at the 5% level (Hair, Ringle and Sarstedt, 2011). The second step is to check the composite reliability (CR) in which the rule of thumb is above 0.70 (Hair et al., 2019). The third step to measure the convergent is Average Variance Extracted (AVE). The AVE is obtained by averaging the indicator reliabilities of a construct. The criterion for AVE is the value should be 0.5 (50%) or higher (Hair et al., 2019). The following table 2 shows the validity of the observed variables for exogenous variables in order to assess the measurement of this study highlighting the items loading, CR and AVE.

Table 2 : Results of Measurement Model

Construct	Measurement Items	Loading	t-Statistics	AVE	CR
Organizational Effectiveness	I have no difficulties to contact with the TU officials	0.666	16.72	0.584	0.891
	My TU is much helpful regarding protecting my rights	0.500	8.168		
	I have relied on the TU regarding my workplace	0.484	7.368		
	My TU is accountable and transparent for me	0.660	12.876		
	My TU inform me about its operations.	0.662	14.323		
	My TU has the influence over my company's rules and regulations	0.793	30.981		
	My union has lots of power to protect my rights	0.730	22.553		
	My TU shares information about employer and workplace with me	0.761	24.862		
	My TU is responsive to my problems and complaints	0.661	15.452		
Collective Bargaining Effectiveness	TU represents its members satisfactorily	0.772	29.902	0.589	0.875
	TU protects employees against ill-treatment	0.804	37.741		
	TU promotes equality at work	0.763	27.267		
	TU improves and protects employees' working conditions	0.739	26.429		
	We have strong TU with bargaining power	0.625	13.458		
	TU makes a difference to working terms and conditions	0.459	6.466		
	TU resolved grievances timorously	0.514	8.801		

Industrial Relations Climate Effectiveness	There is proper communication between management and unions in my organization	0.508	7.013	0.502	0.833
	In my organization union and management work together to make a better place in which to work	0.625	11.318		
	In my organization union and management have respect for each other's goals	0.640	10.498		
	My organization safeguards and advances workers' interest	0.538	8.546		
	My organization improved terms and conditions of employment	0.717	18.748		
	Union and management in my organization tend to dislike each other	0.694	14.429		
	Grievances are normally settled promptly in my organization	0.504	8.042		
Buyers' Codes of Conduct	Buyers' Codes of Conduct practices protect the unfairness in the working place.	0.512	8.799	0.533	0.850
	Buyers' Codes of Conduct make sure that everyone is safe in work environment.	0.724	17.35		
	Buyers' Codes of Conduct encourage to organize association	0.739	18.54		
	Buyers' Codes of Conduct encourage collective bargaining.	0.663	12.43		
	Buyers' Codes of Conduct helps to solve dispute.	0.779	23.25		
	RMG industries are very much alert to maintaining buyers' codes of conduct.	0.740	17.22		

Trade Union Effectiveness	TUs of my organization negotiate for pay, benefits, and working conditions for workers	0.754	17.929	0.671	0.910
	TUs assure membership growth	0.785	22.457		
	TUs increase my commitment	0.901	68.325		
	TUs protect me against unfair treatment	0.875	53.195		
	TUs improve my job security	0.777	30.121		

* The highlighted items were discarded due to their loading value resulting below 0.60

The accomplishment of the necessities of convergent validity, 0.6 was indomitable as the least cut-off value for the items loading. Accordingly, seven items OE2, OE3, CBE6, CBE7, IRCE1, IRCE4, IRCE7, and BCoC1 failed to meet the minimum criteria. However, to achieve the minimum acceptable value of AVE and for the goodness of fit (GoF) of the measurement model, items OE2, OE3, CBE6, CBE7, IRCE1, IRCE4, IRCE7, and BCoC1 were discarded; and PLS was run again (Hair et al., 2011; MacKenzie et al., 2011). Then the loading items were exceeding the threshold of 0.6 and fulfill the requirements of the level of AVE and CR. Table 2 confirmed that the 26 items were sufficient to represent their respective construct.

4.1.2 Discriminant Validity

After the assessment of the convergent validity and if the required criteria are fulfilled that is if the results of the items loading, AVE, and CR fulfill the requirements of the level then it needs to measure the discriminant validity. This technique assesses the distinctiveness of a construct. Fornell and Larcker Criteria and heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) (Henseler et al., 2015) are the two techniques to measure the convergent validity of the measurement model. The criteria of assessing convergent validity using the Fornell and Larcker techniques is that if loadings of an item within a construct are higher than the loading of items of any other construct within the same column then the constructs are assumed as valid (Gefen, Straub and Boudreau, 2000). In the case of HTMT, researchers can apply cutoff scores such as 0.90 to interpret their HTMT results. Additionally, Franke and Sarstedt (2019) recently suggested supplementary significance testing that includes confidence intervals to further assess HTMT ratios and discriminant validity. As shown in table 3, all the values passed the recommended values. Table 4 demonstrates that HTMT inference also shows that the confidence interval did not show a value of 0.90 in any of the constructs of this study.

Table 3 : Fornell-Larcker Correlation Check

Construct	CBE	IRCE	OE	BCoC	TUE
CBE	0.802				
IRCE	0.768	0.709			
OE	0.612	0.594	0.764		
BCoC	0.755	0.641	0.601	0.730	
TUE	0.649	0.497	0.698	0.466	0.819

Note : Diagonals (in bold) represent the squared root of the average variance extracted (AVE) while the other entries represent the correlations.

Table 4 : Heterotrit-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) Criteria

Construct	CBE	IRCE	OE	BCoC	TUE
CBE					
IRCE	0.836				
OE	0.802	0.790			
BCoC	0.382	0.564	0.528		
TUE	0.776	0.727	0.806	0.370	

4.2 Assessment of Structural Model

After the measurement model assessment then it needs to assess the structural model, which relies heavily on multiple regression analysis. To perform the measurement of the structural model, the first step is to assess the structural model constructs to verify if high multicollinearity is a problem. The variance inflation factor (VIF) values of the items should be below 5.0 to have free from high multicollinearity and suitable for assessing structural model in case of the indicators on reflective constructs (Hair et al., 2014). This study shows the VIF values between 1.177 and 3.160 indicate that the items are not problematic for assessing the structural model. The predictive relevance that is Q^2 of a reflective model is assessed by using the tool of cross-validated redundancy. The Q^2 value is considered for the reflectively modeled endogenous factor (Geisser, 2012). The Q^2 value higher than zero tells that the exogenous constructs have prognostic relevance for the endogenous constructs (Hair et al., 2011). This value is calculated by using the blindfolding algorithm that omits every 7th data point for the indicators. As per the analyzed data, the model is considered to have predictive relevance. More specifically, the Q^2 value for TUE of this study is 0.391 and BCoC is 0.450 is more than 0 indicating that the model has sufficient predictive relevance. In this study, the coefficient determination (R^2) is a joint impact of exogenous variables on the endogenous variable. The lowest effect of R^2 is 0, and the highest is 1 Hair Jr et al. (2017) demonstrate that on endogenous variables, the R^2 values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 can be considered large, moderate, and weak respectively. This study found R^2 of BCoC showing as 0.558 and TUE

as 0.601, which emphasizes that the exogenous variables OE, CBE and IRCE can describe 55.8% of the variability in BCoC and 60.1% of the variability in their effective TUs. The mediation of BCoC increases the variability effects from 55.8% to 60.1% resulting from the positive significant mediating effects on the endogenous variable (TUE).

4.3 Summary of Path Coefficient and Hypothesis Testing

The results of the hypotheses are summarized in Table 5 shows that all hypotheses were supported. The findings are discussed after the data analysis in the next section.

Table 5 : Result of the Structural Model Assessment for Direct Relations

H	Relation	Std. β	SE	t-values	p-values	f ²	Decision
H1a	OE→TUE	0.496	0.061	8.108	0.000	0.055	Accepted
H1b	OE→BCoC	0.349	0.041	5.409	0.000	0.043	Accepted
H2a	CBE→TUE	0.157	0.059	2.861	0.000	0.023	Accepted
H2b	CBE→BCoC	0.145	0.049	2.661	0.000	0.033	Accepted
H3a	IRCE→TUE	0.204	0.052	3.934	0.000	0.039	Accepted
H3b	IRCE→BCoC	0.534	0.024	19.168	0.000	1.021	Accepted
H4	BCoC→TUE	0.542	0.052	9.421	0.000	0.321	Accepted

Note : $p < 0.05$, (based on Two-tailed test with 5000 bootstrapping)

Table 6 : Results of the Structural Model Assessment for Specific Indirect Effects

H	Relation	Std. β	SE	t-values	p-values	Decision
H5	OE → BCoC → TUE	0.051	0.018	2.350	0.000	Accepted
H6	CBE → BCoC → TUE	0.062	0.016	3.103	0.000	Accepted
H7	IRCE → BCoC → TUE	0.407	0.049	8.751	0.000	Accepted

5. DISCUSSION, IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDA

The analysis of the data obtained from the survey of this study shows a strong positive significant relationship between the OE and TUs effectiveness ($\beta = 0.496$, $t=8.108$, $p < 0.000$) and such finding support the previous research by Bryson (2003); Burchielli (2004); Fiorito et al. (1995) and Hammer and Wazeter (1993). This study finds a positive relationship between the CBE and TUs Effectiveness. The analyzed data indicates that CBE ($\beta = 0.157$, $t=2.861$, $p<0.000$), positively influences on TUs effectiveness which means H2 is significantly accepted. Previous research studies by Carr (2014), Hayter (2011), and Huynh (2015) showed that effective collective bargaining plays a significant role in the improvements of pay, working environments, and fair treatment to create trust and reciprocal respect between management, workers, and their organizations, and contribute in bringing up strong and effective TUs in the organization. CB is encouraged in RMG in Bangladesh (Absar, 2012) to ensure effective TUs (Hayter, 2011; Marginson & Galetto, 2016). The analysis also

shows the significant positive relation between IRCE and TU effectiveness which is supported by previous studies conducted by Dastmalchian et al. (1982); Deery et al., (1999), and Newman et al. (2019). From Table 5, the result of hypothesis H3 exhibits that IRCE ($\beta = 0.204$, $t=3.934$, $p<0.000$) has significantly positive relations of IRCE with TUs effectiveness in the RMG industry in Bangladesh. Moreover, OE, CBE, and IRCE have significant positive impacts on BCoC. The respondents think that OE, CBE, and IRCE are significant motivators in making TUs effective, and such finding supported by the previous research by Abun et al. (2018); Ahamed (2013); Alam et al. (2018); Ansary and Barua (2015); Azad et al. (2019); Hossain and Arefin (2015) and Kaium (2020). These studies have been conducted on the OE, CBE and IRCE and its effect on the BCoC argued that BCoC as a crucial part of the RMG industry which puts more pressure on a healthy and positive working environment and effective TUs. Accord on Fire and Building Safety and Alliances for Bangladesh Workers Safety-these two alliances of IBs and their codes of conduct have also significant effect on the RMG sector of Bangladesh which creates sound IRs, thereby growing the green RMG industry for the betterment and interests of the TUs (Hasan, 2018). The result of the present study shows that the roles of BCoC are very important for establishing and maintaining sound TUs in the industry under study. Table 6 shows the mediating effect of BCoC to establish whether it mediated the relationships between OE, CBE, IRCE and TUE. BCoC ($\beta = 0.051$, $t = 2.350$, $p=0.000$) mediated the relationship between OE and TUs effectiveness; BCoC ($\beta = 0.062$, $t = 3.103$, $p=0.000$) mediated the relationship between CBE and TUs effectiveness and BCoC ($\beta = 0.407$, $t = 8.751$, $p=0.000$) also mediated the relationship between IRCE and TUs effectiveness. Therefore, this study has identified our components such as OE, CBE, IRCE and BCoC to measure the TUs effectiveness in protecting the workers' rights from the perspective of the RMG industry of Bangladesh. These constructs were significantly linked with the effectiveness of TUs where BCoC mediate and increases the effectiveness of TUs in protecting the rights of the workers in the RMG industry in Bangladesh.

Examining the objectives of this study adds new dimensions to the literature. The findings help to explain prior empirical work, which established a positive relationship among organizational, collective bargaining and industrial relations climate effectiveness, buyers' codes of conduct and TUs effectiveness (Yao & Zhong, 2013). Second, the important theoretical contribution of this study shows by explaining the perceptions of the workers towards the effectiveness of TUs helps to ensure job security of workers and to capitalize human resources. Under such circumstances, it might be considered that workers believe on the perception that a favorable relationship between management and TUs creates trust in management and assure greater job security. In the same way, it might also look forward to when workers believe the TUs is effective in representing their rights and interests, they will also be more likely to perform highly for the organization (Ma et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2013). The findings of this study have significant policy implications in the Bangladeshi context. It is suggested that TUs should arrange its collective platform

in terms of increasing communication with TUs members. Moreover, it needs in understanding the BCoC to improve the TUs members' perception regarding the effectiveness TUs. It is also recommended to the policymaker to initiate trustworthy lawful systems and well-built enforcement of laws and BCoC which will provide authority and control to TUs and effective labor inspections because some workers claim the TUs do not have enough legal power to deal with their rights and interests. This study suggests that policymakers give more emphasis on brand development of TUs to change the negative image of it because a positive image would help improve the perceptions of all stakeholders, which will develop a constructive relationship between the workers and TUs.

This study does not free from its limitations. Firstly, the present study is conducted on particular union members and workers that is RMG industry. As such, the findings of this research cannot be generalized because the uniqueness and surroundings of the TUs in the RMG industry may vary from other TUs in the country (Hammer & Wazeter 1993). For this, having an overall picture, it needs to conduct a future study on the TUs of different sectors of the country. Secondly, the sample of this study was small and picked from the union members and non-union members of the RMG industry in Bangladesh thus the power of generalization might be limited. Therefore, future studies may consider a larger sample size and collect the data from all parties of the sector under study such as managers, owners, buyers, etc. Thirdly, the developed conceptual model was embodying industry-specific, particularly for the RMG industry in Bangladesh. The results of this study might not explain the same problem from a different perspective even in the same industry in a different economy. Therefore, in the next researchers may consider the different economies to get an overall picture. Finally, yet importantly, in the future, cross-cultural study of trade unionism and workers' rights may be conducted.

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